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Students' profile engaged in vet programmes in the catalan context

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Abstract

Vocational education and training (VET) is considered a strategic pathway for tackling early leaving, improving young people's educational level and their opportunities for gaining access to the job market. This work contributes to VET research line through the description of the personal and academic profile of all those students who are involved in itineraries of secondary VET according to the multidimensional construct of student engagement. Focused on a sample of 761 young people who, during 2014-2015 academic year, were involved in Catalan VET programmes of level 2 (named CFGM) of Barcelona city and its surrounding area, results show a young people's 'non-controversial' personal and academic profile. This first approach to these youngsters' profile contribute to a better knowledge and understanding of why they have decided to enrol in VET pathways, and if they want to continue or leave them.

Keywords

student engagement; VET pathways; early leaving; young people

1. Introduction

The rate of Spanish early leavers is characterized for being one of the higher rates in the European context (MECD, 2015, 2017). VET is being considered a strategic pathway for tackling early leaving, improving the educational level of young people and their opportunities for gaining access to the job market (CEDEFOP, 2016a, European Commission/Eacea/Eurydice/Cedefop, 2014, OECD, 2014). In this respect, development of studies and researches on VET becomes strategic.

This work, which is the initial phase of a longitudinal research on VET that is working, wants to contribute to VET research line through the description of the profile of all those students who are engaged in VET programmes of level 2 (named CFGM) in the Catalan context.

The aim is to achieve a better knowledge and understanding of the profile of all those students who are involved in these itineraries of secondary VET, focusing on their features (personal variables, sociodemographic characteristics, economic situation, health state, etc.), motivations for choosing the VET track, their educational and professional expectations, to name a few. Likewise, the analysis of these students' profile has to be done also from the perspective of policies on tackling early school leaving (Abiétar-López, Marhuenda-Fluixá, & Navas-Saurin, 2017; Cedefop, 2016b).

As we can see hereinafter, results show a young people's profile in Catalan VET programmes characterized by a 'non-controversial' personal and academic profile. Nevertheless, despite this 'positive' profile, it is highlighting the presence of variables that could be 'critical' such as health perception, economic situation, or factors that determine their possible intention of leaving VET studies.

This first analysis and description of these youngsters' profile contributes to a better understanding of the reasons because most of these young people decide to enrol in these VET pathways and because they want to continue or leave them.

2. VET in the Spanish education system

Understanding better VET in the Spanish education system leads us to show here the main characteristics of the education system in Spain.

Since the 2014-2015 academic year, LOMCE (2013) is the Educational Act that regulates Education in Spain. This Educational Act regulates all the educational system that is characterized for having compulsory and non-compulsory educational stages.

Compulsory education is offered from primary schooling (compulsory education of 6 years addressed to learners aged 6 to 12) till the end of lower compulsory secondary educational (ESO in Spanish) –this is the last stage of compulsory education comprising four academic years from 12 to 16 years old–.

Non-compulsory education is offered in different educational stages. We could talk about two non-compulsory phases. The first one is childhood (for children aged 0 to 6 years). The second one is high school (Baccalaureate) and/or VET studies (basic –FPB in Spanish and PFI in Catalan–, intermediate –CFGM in Spanish– and higher VET programmes –CFGS in Spanish–).

The access to this second non-compulsory phase is after graduation in ESO. When learners end ESO, they receive the lower secondary education certificate (ESO diploma) which gives access to high school, intermediate VET or the labour market.

Intermediate VET (CFGM) in Spain is formed by 26 vocational families and run in a 1-year or 2-year programme (depends on the programme) between 1,400 and 2,000 hours of training. This training period is also divided between the formative centre and the workplace.

It is worth saying that traditionally, VET pathway in the Spanish context has been a second chance in front of the academic one (Baccalaureate and University). However, in the last years the number of students' enrolment in VET itinerary has increased, due to the fact of the improvement of VET attractiveness, although despite this growth in VET enrolment, the number of students who opt for academic pathway is still higher than the number of students who opt for VET (Sancha & Gutiérrez, 2016). This data lead us to conclude that although the improvement is evident, it is needed to continue working on the visibility and attractive of VET.

3. Method

Data came from the application of a questionnaire that was designed based on the multidimensional construct of student engagement. Its design takes into account other instruments such as SEI –Student Engagement Instrument– (Appleton, 2012), TEDP –Trousse d'évaluation des de décrocheurs potentiels– (Janosz et al., 2007), Social Support Scale (Landeta & Calvete 2002), MSPSS questionnaire (Zimet, Dahlem, Zimet y Farley 1988), FMC-Q –Questionnaire of family motivation– (Alonso, Simón & Asensio, 2013), studies of VET leaving in France (Lannegrand, Cosnefroy & Lecigne, 2012), Denmark (Tangaard, 2013) and Australia (Callan, 2005), and study of social support for school engagement (Wan & Eccles, 2012).

The instrument has four dimensions although this work is focused only on personal and academic one. This dimension is integrated by personal, social, demographic, family and economic variables –see age, gender, immigrant condition, family situation, health, economic and work situation, etc.–, and by academic variables linked to current studies, itineraries, and school biography –see repetition rates, previous school situation, access paths to VET studies, reasons for the choice of studies, intention and reasons for abandonment, etc.–.

The questionnaire was submitted to an external validation –14 external experts validated the instrument– and an internal validation –internal consistency was measured with reliability analysis–, and was authorized by the ethic committee of research from University of Illes Balears.

After this previous validation, the questionnaire was applied to a sample of 761 young people who, during 2015-2016 academic year, were involved in Catalan VET programmes (CFGM) of Barcelona city and its surrounding area (Badalona, Sant Adria, Hospitalet and Sta. Coloma). The application of the questionnaire had the authorization and consent of educational centres and family and/or tutors of all those young people under aged.

Data were subjected to descriptive statistical exploitation –frequencies of the analysis dimension– through the statistical package for the social sciences SPSS (17.0 version).

4. Results

Results show a sample of young people in CFGM programmes where males (66.3%) are more representative than women (33.7%). Likewise, 65.4% of these young people are domestic youths (65.4% were born in Catalonia), being 30.7% of them foreign youngsters who were born in other countries of European Union (69.3%) and Central and South America (20%). 80% of the sample are young people aged less than 20 years and 91.6% of them live with their parents. Likewise, 87.5 of these young people say not to be working.

Regarding their parents' profile, about 60% were born in Catalonia, 45% have compulsory studies, 25% non-compulsory secondary studies, and 72% are working.

About their economic situation, 60% of these young people say not to have or only have some economic difficulty. Despite this percentage, it is worth noting that 23.4% recognise medium economic difficulties and 17.7% recognise lots economic difficulties.

In regards with their health perception, 87.3% of these young people have a good health perception although it is highlighting identify some group of youths with diseases like depression, anorexia, bulimia, etc. (18.4%) or some addictions like alcohol, drugs, game, etc. (13.1%).

Focusing the attention on their academic variables, 74.1% of the sample have secondary compulsory studies ended and this has been their access pathway to the CFGM programme.

Taking into consideration some previous academic variables such as repetition rates or expulsion from school, it is worthwhile noting that 47.8% repeated ESO and 13.2% repeated primary studies, and that 26.7% were expelled from school, being 90.1% of these expulsions temporary.

Regarding the current VET studies, young people of this sample are involved in CFGM programmes, which most representative professional families are administration (10.4%), commerce and marketing (10.2%), IT (18%), health (13.4%) and hospitality sector (9.5%). About their reasons for accessing to these studies, 61.1% argue they like these studies. Likewise, 50.7% say someone recommended these studies to them. The main recommendation sources are families (50.3%), friends (35.8 %), teachers (27.1%) and counsellors (18%).

To conclude, it is worth noting young people's intention of dropout their current VET studies. 74.2% of them say not to have any intention of leaving their studies although 25.8% say that yes. The main reasons for leaving these studies are personal reasons (30.7%) and learning difficulties (39.1%). In addition to these reasons, they also point out others such as 'I

don't like it (16.7%), *It is difficult* (19.3%) and *Family reasons* (10.4%) —usually related to their family's economic situation—.

5. Conclusions

Overall, results show a young people's profile in Catalan VET programmes characterized by a 'non-controversial' personal and academic profile. As we saw before, 66.2% are domestic students, 91.6% are living with their parents and 97.3% do not have children, 81.6% have a good health perception, 30.8% identify an economic situation without difficulties, 61.1% identify 'because I like it' as the main reason for their VET study selection, and 74.2% say do not want to leave the selected VET studies.

Despite these 'positive' responses, it is interesting focus the attention on other ones that could be turn into 'critical' variables such as the risk of 12.7% of young people who do not have a good health perception, the economic difficulties that 69.3% of students say to have, or the intention of leaving VET studies of 25.8% of youngsters who argue reasons linked to personal factors or learning difficulties, to give some examples.

In an initial stage, to know young people's backgrounds, interests, motivations, future prospects, academic and labour expectations, etc. in VET programmes is crucial to understanding why they have decided to enrol in these VET pathways and if they want to continue or leave them. Then, according to this, to promote initiatives for working with them on their success. That is, make to emerge VET as an alternative for tackling early leaving and improving young people's opportunities for their social, educational and labour inclusion.

To conclude, as we said in the introduction section, this work wants to contribute to the aim of minimizing early school leaving rates, increasing education levels and improving young people's access to the job market through VET pathways. To this end, we therefore believe that results presented here are the first step for its achievement because show the analysis of variables which, when combined, play a decisive role in describing and understanding why young people have the opportunity, or take the decision, to succeed as well as the risk of failure within these VET pathways.

This work, as the initial phase of a longitudinal research that is working, give us clues for stepping us research into these Pathways leading to success in, or dropout from, vocational training in the education system at levels 1 and 2.

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